

DEVELOPMENT OF A ROBOTIC-ENABLED COMPOSITE PART HIGH-RESOLUTION INSPECTION AND REVERSE-DIGITAL TWIN TOOL

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) are widely used in aerospace and automotive industries due to their excellent mechanical properties. However, detecting manufacturing defects such as scratches, delamination and wrinkles remains challenging, particularly for small to medium-sized manufacturers who lack affordable automated inspection solutions. This paper presents two automated computer vision systems designed to address this gap; a 2D imaging system for large, flat structures, and a 3D imaging system for smaller components with complex geometries. Both systems utilise a robot mounted computer vision camera and a custom image stitching pipeline, implemented using open-source software to generate high-fidelity composite images or 3D models. Defect detection is implemented using a YOLOv8n convolutional neural network. Initial testing of the 2D system on a turbine blade demonstrates effective defect identification within 8 minutes, producing a 585 megapixel composite image. The proposed framework offers a low-cost, easily deployable inspection solution to enhance quality control and support industry 4.0 initiatives in composite manufacturing.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced polymers (CFRP) possess advantages such as low density, high specific strength, and low coefficient of thermal expansion, and are widely used in aerospace, automobile, and construction materials [1,2]. However, various manufacturing defects, such as voids, delamination, wrinkles and foreign objects, are practically inevitable due to the complexity of the manufacturing process [3,4].

Computer Vision (CV) has proven itself to be a simple, fast and low-cost solution to automated detection of CFRP manufacturing surface defects [5]. The use of CV for automated detection of surface defects (among other quality controls) within the aerospace industry is well established [6], however smaller institutions such as small to medium sized manufacturers of composite components and structures often lack the budget or resources to develop their own automated solutions to often manual processes such as visual inspection, in particular for complex geometric parts. Furthermore, the proprietary inspection methods developed by the larger institutions often remain undisclosed with little detail entering the literature or industry reports, making it more difficult for smaller institutions to develop this capability.

There are many challenges faced when visual inspection is manual, including; challenges in securing labour, the training required for each new person, the variability of each individual (skill/practice level, natural ability, speed etc.), the variability within each individual human with regards to concentration and energy levels, motivation etc. which could change throughout a single day as well as on separate days. There are many changeable areas which can lead to a variable outcome or inconsistencies in reliability, which is undesirable within the manufacturing and quality control of potentially safety critical components.

Automating visual inspection offers improvements in all of these areas as well as reduces cost and allows for the workforce to be redeployed in other critical areas of production. In general, the literature supports higher success in defect detection with fewer defect-misses by computer vision systems when compared with human inspection [7–12]. However, from those same studies, there is a definite consensus that CV offers much more with regards to repeatability and speed. While the use of computer vision inspection has grown rapidly in recent years, and the techniques encompassed within this area are used widely throughout industry for many applications, the area is ever-expanding and is crucial for facilitating movement towards Industry 4.0.

Machine learning, more specifically convolutional neural networks (CNNs) with regards to CV, has also proven itself in recent years as a significant addition to defect detection, showing improvements in accuracy, speed and overall automation in general [13] with studies showing their efficacy in detecting visual surface defects with success rates of 90% and above [11,14].

However, the current offerings of computer vision systems are dominated by single 2D image capture inspection solutions with few options for capturing, measuring and evaluating the geometry and surface of manufactured parts in 3D or in high or even Gigapixel resolution.

In-order to facilitate the generation of full-scale high-resolution image sets, multiple images would need to be captured from different camera placements and subsequently stitched together using CV techniques. This would be very difficult and labour intensive to conduct manually as the accuracy of a hand-held camera placement and resulting image quality (which can be affected by the stability of the camera) is paramount. The camera may also need to be held in positions not easily reachable by a human being (particularly for large composite structures such as wind turbine blades, airplane fuselages etc.) while ensuring imaging accuracy.

Compiling a set of local images into one single digital image record requires a method of stitching the images together. Stitching the images into one large composite image/model is important for providing easily discernible and intuitive context on defect locations for human operators. This is a requirement as it will more readily facilitate determining subsequent action following defect detection, whether this might be rework, tagging, further investigation or scrapping the component.

This system is intended to be low cost and simple to implement, with the aim being that small to medium sized composite manufacturers could easily implement such a system without requiring a large budget and extensive resources.

This work will explore the potential of two fully automated imaging and defect detection systems for achieving this. Both systems automatically provide a digital record for easy further analysis or to refer back to at a later date, which is highly beneficial and often lacking in manual inspection practices:

1. 2D Imaging system – Intended for large and generally flat composite structures such as large planar composite panels and turbine blades. The output from this system will be a very high-resolution composite stitched image with surface defects highlighted in bounding boxes.
2. 3D Imaging system – Intended for smaller components with complex geometry. The output from this system will be a 3D model (reverse digital twin) of the component with a low-resolution surface texture and defects highlighted in bounding boxes.

This work introduces the term ‘reverse digital twin’ to describe a digital record created from the as-manufactured physical part, such as a 3D model generated via scanning or photogrammetry. Unlike a traditional digital twin, which typically begins with the original CAD model and supports manufacturing and operation of the physical object, the reverse digital twin is derived from the final manufactured artifact and exists digitally. This representation captures real-world characteristics such as the true manufactured geometry, deviations, surface finish and wear. This makes it valuable for quality assurance, maintenance, comparison against nominal designs and general record keeping.

The reverse digital twin serves as a digital snapshot of the physical part’s actual state, bridging the gap between nominal CAD models and reality, much like how photography and computer vision help document finished products but with the added dimensional and geometric context of a 3D model.

2 METHODOLOGY

This section will provide an overview of both systems architecture and how images are captured and processed within the automated pipeline. Both systems share the same general structure with regard to hardware:

- A Kuka iiwa R820 collaborative robot and Sunrise controller were utilised to hold and move a vision camera to pre-programmed positions.
- The camera mounted to the robot arm was a Basler Ace 2 (20MP) with a 35mm lens. This was connected to a PC running OpenCV.
- The PC and the Sunrise controller communicate over TCP/IP, when the robot reaches a new position it will pause for 0.5 seconds and then send a 'Take Image' command to the PC where OpenCV receives it and captures and stores the image.
- Once the robot has completed all positions it sends a 'Stitch' command to OpenCV and then terminates the connection, OpenCV will then move onto the next step in the pipeline, which differs for the two systems.

Defect Detection:

The defect detection method is the same for both systems, through OpenCV v4.11.0 [15,16] a YOLOv8n [17] model was trained and used. This model is still under development and so far, has only been trained on one type of surface defect (scratch) which is currently present on a turbine blade which is being used to develop the 2D system. In the current model a training set of 96 images has been used, consisting of 23 original images and 73 augmented images. All training images were resized to a resolution of 1280 x 1280 pixels.

Lighting:

Lighting is a key component of all computer vision systems, it is important that there is enough light for a correct exposure level while also ensuring a suitable shutter speed [18]. This is particularly important for the YOLO model, as suboptimal lighting conditions can reduce successful object/defect recognition in some CNNs by more than 20% [18]. To solve this problem, a lighting frame was constructed out of extruded aluminium profile with one main centre panel measuring 1m across and two side panels measuring 0.5m across which fold against the main panel for storage. LED strip lighting is then held across the full span of the frame by way of hook and loop tape and the cross members in the centre panel can be moved up and down to adjust the height of each light strip. This frame allows for light to be spread across the full surface of any component from all angles, the frame is shown as part of the 2D imaging system later in Figure 3.

2D System:

The overall architecture of the 2D system can be seen below, in Figure 1.

Figure 1: 2D System Architecture

For the 2D system, a custom stitching algorithm was required for the reasons below:

- It needs to ensure true representation of the surface geometry in a way that does not risk feature distortion. Therefore, the only transformation applied to each image will be translation, there will be no rotation of the camera between images to remove the need for any image warping steps in the stitching process.
- It needs to align the images accurately and reliably without the feature detection and matching steps of traditional image stitching techniques being impacted by the repeating patterns, or sometimes featureless surfaces, of CFRP.
- There are no readily available stitching models or software to account for the requirements above.

To ensure true representation of the surface geometry with no warping, the robot arm was programmed to capture all images in a 2D grid pattern with a perfectly level camera normal to the imaging plane for all images, therefore allowing translational movement only with no rotational movement between images. As shown in Figure 2, camera rotation can result in surface geometry being skewed or distorted if the camera is not positioned normal to the surface, requiring a warping step during stitching to correct this in an attempt to fit them together correctly with the other images, which is undesirable for this application.

Figure 2: Camera Rotation vs Camera Translation [19]

In order to not allow the feature detection and matching steps to be impacted by the repeating patterns or sometimes featureless surfaces of CFRP (depending on the material), the stitching algorithm utilises the known robot cartesian coordinates from each camera position to align the images relative to one another.

The full homography relationship connecting 2D coordinates of features in the captured image, or on the camera sensor, to the 3D world coordinates of the same features through camera position and intrinsic properties is given in Equation 1. Removing the rotational matrix from the equation greatly simplifies the relationship between the position of features in the image and the real-world. From here, the camera intrinsic properties (f_x , f_y , c_x and c_y together represent internal camera characteristics such as focal length and optical centre) can be provided by way of prior camera calibration and the real-world coordinates can then also be supplied by knowing the robot positions for each image.

$$s \begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_x & 0 & c_x \\ 0 & f_y & c_y \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} r_{11} & r_{12} & r_{13} \\ r_{21} & r_{22} & r_{23} \\ r_{31} & r_{32} & r_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} t_1 \\ t_2 \\ t_3 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

From this, Equations 2 and 3 can be used to determine t_x and t_y , the translational movement of each image (in pixels) within the image coordinate system ($t_z = 0$ as the camera only moves in an xy grid). f_x and f_y represent the focal length in pixels by combining lens focal length and sensor pixel dimensions, these are obtained from the intrinsic matrix through camera calibration. dX and dY are the camera translational movement (in mm) and S is the scene depth (distance from the camera to the scene/surface, in mm).

$$t_x = \frac{f_x dX}{S} \quad (2)$$

$$t_y = \frac{f_y dY}{S} \quad (3)$$

Following image placement, seam finding and blending are performed using functions provided by the OpenCV library v4.11.0. There is a 30% overlap across all images taken in the grid pattern, this is to allow for seam finding and blending to successfully account for potential minor pixel misalignments between neighbouring images.

SAHI (Slicing Aided Hyper Inference) [20] was also utilised with YOLO for the 2D system to breakdown the very high-resolution stitched image into tiles for individual inspection. This is required to perform the defect detection step on the composite image as a whole. This method was chosen over performing the inspection on each individual image prior to stitching them all together as the output from the latter method results in slight breaks and misalignments in the bounding boxes and inconsistencies in confidence values shown in the final composite when a defect is split across multiple images.

Figure 3: 2D Imaging System Inspecting a Turbine Blade

3D System:

The overall architecture of the 3D system can be seen below, Figure 4.

Figure 4: 3D System Architecture

As can be seen above, the 3D system is very similar to the 2D system however the image acquisition is from different angles around the component rather than in a 2D grid and the stitching takes place in open-source photogrammetry software AliceVision Meshroom [21], where a 3D model is generated as the output (reverse digital twin). The camera intrinsic properties (f_x , f_y , c_x and c_y representing focal length and optical centre) are also given to Meshroom to simplify the homography calculations and to allow the software to accurately account for scaling. Meshroom also creates a surface texture from the image set which is wrapped around the 3D model generated to provide a realistic representation of the component exterior. Command line interface (CLI) is also utilised to integrate Meshroom into the automated pipeline by allowing communication between the Python script running OpenCV and Meshroom.

3 TESTING AND RESULTS

2D System:

This inspection system completed a full automated inspection of a 1.32m length of the composite turbine blade in 8 minutes and 15 seconds while highlighting 3 surface scratches, the system output image can be seen in Figure 5.

The PC used to run OpenCV for image stitching and defect detection in this system was a Dell Precision 7680 laptop, equipped with a Core i7-13850 CPU, 32 GB of RAM and an Nvidia RTX 2000 Ada GPU with 8 GB of VRAM.

The output image is 585Megapixels and generated from 62 raw images in total.

<u>System Element</u>	<u>Time</u>
Capturing images	5 mins 10 secs
Stitching images	50 secs
Defect detection	2 mins 15 secs
Total	8 mins 15 secs

Table 1: Time Breakdown of 2D System Operation

Figure 5: 2D System Output

With the seam finding and blending operations switched off inside the stitching algorithm, the total time of the system is reduced by 30 seconds, making the total 7 minutes and 45 seconds. This would reduce the stitching quality but would still fulfil the function of permitting defect identification and location context. There is also some potential for optimisation of the robot movement and image capture phase.

This could also be brought down by a further 1 minute and 45 seconds if SAHI was not used for the defect detection step and each individual image was processed by the YOLO model and marked where required before stitching. This would also create a slightly less desirable output but would still fulfil the function of detecting and highlighting defects on the single compiled output image. If this modification was implemented, the total time is 6 minutes for a fully automated inspection.

4 DISCUSSION

The results so far demonstrate that the proposed 2D system can complete a fully autonomous inspection of large composite structures in a reasonably small timeframe and effectively identify surface defects with high accuracy.

Furthermore, this framework is simple and relatively budget friendly to implement, creating a good starting point for small to medium sized composite manufacturers to work with in beginning their inspection automation journey. There is also opportunity to reduce cost even further by implementing this system with a simple cartesian robot, which would also easily allow for a larger inspection reach compared to the Kuka iiwa used here. This would however limit operation strictly to the 2D system but at the same time would create an in-expensive and effective approach to automated visual inspection of composite panels and other large structures.

The LED strip lighting could be further optimised by including a diffuser for each strip. It can clearly be seen in Figure 5 that there are strong reflections on the turbine blade surface, this is not ideal for defect detection, as it provides extra variability in visual input which the YOLO model needs to overcome and could lead to more false negatives. An even exposure is needed over the full surface of the blade to reduce differences in pixel luminosity between the brighter and darker areas.

To simplify the setup and reduce costs even more, the lighting frame could be replaced by a simple large, powerful and diffused ring light mounted with the camera on the robot. The lighting frame was constructed as part of this work due to the requirement in early development of a stationary and wide-spread light source to reduce the negative impact a moving light source has on feature detection and matching which were already disadvantaged due to the repeating patterns. However, these steps were subsequently not needed once known camera positions were implemented.

However, a possible improvement to the 2D system could be to re-introduce feature detection and matching and use them to refine image alignment once the initial placement has been attained from the robot positional coordinates, this is common practice in systems where rough camera positions are known [22,23]. The reason for this is because there are stitching artifacts in the composite image, in earlier development of the system a smaller section of a flat surface was used instead of the turbine blade which led to very close alignment across all images without any refinement needed, but imaging across larger areas reduces the accuracy of each position relative to the others for the Kuka iiwa.

A possible extension of this tool includes modifying the 2D system to include a thermal camera and heat source, this would provide a very simple and effective automated thermography system for large composite structures. Such a system is currently lacking within the literature as well as in commercial offerings. The stitching algorithm developed within this work would be ideally suited to thermography as well due to the lack of features common in thermal imaging.

The model and scene scaling within the 3D system is handled by providing the calculated intrinsic camera properties. Testing is still yet to confirm the accuracy of this method. A potentially more accurate method would be to have one or more reference objects in the scene, such as a calibrated cube, which the system can use as a reference to scale the scene correctly.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This work has demonstrated the feasibility of an automated computer vision inspection system for composite components. The 2D imaging system successfully created a very high-resolution image of a large composite structure, identifying surface defects such as scratches with promising accuracy and efficiency. The integration of robot assisted image acquisition, simple but effective custom stitching algorithms, known camera positions and YOLO-based defect detection creates a practical, cost-effective solution ideally suited to small to medium sized manufacturers.

This framework represents a key step towards industry 4.0 in the wider realm of composite manufacturing by providing scalable and adaptable automated inspection tools that can be implemented easily without the need for large budgets and resources. By making automation more accessible, smaller manufacturers can improve product quality, reduce costs and increase competitiveness.

6 FUTURE WORK

While initial results are encouraging, further work is needed to see both systems working fully. The defect detection model requires more training to include a wider range of defect types and diversity to improve robustness, the 3D imaging system's accuracy and integration need validation and the light source needs to be diffused.

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